

Enhancing Handwritten Digit Recognition with Modern ML Algorithms: A Case Study on USPS Data

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Abstract— Handwritten digit recognition has recently been of very interest among the researchers because of the evolution of various Machine Learning, Deep Learning and Computer Vision algorithms, this paper deals with an handwritten digit recognition system and a method of extraction of characteristics based on the digit form, this method is tested on the USPS handwritten isolated digit database (20000 images in learning and 1500 images in test). In this report, I compare the results of some of the most widely used Machine Learning Algorithms like SVM, KNN, PCA, LDA, QDA, LRC, MLP, ABC, DTC, HOG + SVM, Bayesian, SGD & RFC this work has achieved approximately 80% of success rate for USPS database identification.

Key Words— SVM, KNN, PCA, LDA, QDA, LRC, MLP, ABC, DTC, HOG + SVM, Bayesian, SGD & RFC

I. INTRODUCTION

HANDWRITTEN digit recognition is the ability of a computer system to recognize the handwritten inputs like digits, characters etc. from a wide variety of sources like emails, papers, images, letters etc. This has been a topic of research for decades. Some of the research areas include signature verification, bank check processing, postal address interpretation from envelopes. A lot of classification techniques using Machine Learning have been developed and used for this like K-Nearest Neighbors, SVM Classifier, Random Forest Classifier etc. but these methods although having the accuracy of 88% are not enough for the real world applications. Here comes the use of Deep Learning. In the past decade, deep learning has become the hot tool for Image Processing, object detection, handwritten digit and character recognition etc. A lot of machine learning tools have been developed like scikit-learn, scipy-image, etc. and pybrains, Keras, Theano, Tensorflow by Google, TFLearn etc. for Deep Learning. These tools make the applications robust and therefore more accurate.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

Our model works in three steps: 1) Preprocessing, 2) Features extraction and 3) Use classification Method. In the preprocessing, we have some basic image processing to separate numbers from real samples or preparing data from dataset (which is reshaped from images to the vectors) and then in the second part, we extract features which is very distinguishable descriptor for digits recognition where we

classification is a supervised learning approach in which the computer program learns from the data input given to it and then uses this learning to classify new observation. This data set may simply be bi-class (like identifying whether the person is male or female or that the mail is spam or non-spam) or it

divide an input image into fixed 28*28 cells and we represent each digit with a vector of features. The summary of several classification methods that used in this paper are: QDA that is a classifier with a quadratic decision boundary, generated by fitting class conditional densities to the data and using Bayes' rule, RFC is a random forest is a meta estimator that fits a number of decision tree classifiers on various sub-samples of the dataset and uses averaging to improve the predictive accuracy and control over-fitting, DTC is a Decision Tree Classifier, repetitively divides the working area(plot) into sub part by identifying lines. repetitively because there may be two distant regions of same class divided by other, MLP is a Multi-layer Perceptron classifier, this model optimizes the log-loss function using LBFGS or stochastic gradient descent and SVM a Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a discriminative classifier formally defined by a separating hyperplane. In other words, given labeled training data (supervised learning), the algorithm outputs an optimal hyperplane which categorizes new examples.

A. Classification

Without any doubt, SVM is one of the successful and most popular supervised learning classifier in machine learning which constructs a hyper-plane in high order space which can be used as classification plane. SVM commonly used with linear, polynomial, RBF and sigmoid kernels. We have used a multiclass SVM classification (libsvm) [6] in our model with different kernels of 1) linear, 2) polynomial, 3) RBF, 4) sigmoid, and details are described in section 3 (results and

may be multi-class too. Some examples of classification problems are: speech recognition, handwriting recognition, bio metric identification, document classification etc.

Figure 1. Recognition Process

Fig. 1. Our method step, starting with preprocessin, then feature extraction and finally classification with each methods and get scores and accuracy of that method..

comparison). As a standard validation, we separated data into two parts of Train and Test according to the baseline In the pre-processing phase is an important process for recognition digit. In this work, the images of the digit are extracted from the standard USPS database, and then noise is reduced finally we normalized the images extracted with size 28 x 28.

Extraction the method used for extraction is based on the form of each digit. Dividing the image on five characteristic zones: West zone, East zone, North zone, South zone and Central zone. These characteristic areas are detected by the dilatation of the image processed in four directions.

USPS Handwritten Digits database of New York University has been used in our model validation. USPS one of the most famous and popular used database for handwritten digits recognition which contains 21,500 samples included two parts of 20,000 and 1,500 samples corresponding to training and test data. The total numbers of instances are shown in figure 2.

Class	Number of samples		
	Train Data	Test Data	Total
'0'	2000	150	2150
'1'	2000	150	2150
'2'	2000	150	2150
'3'	2000	150	2150
'4'	2000	150	2150
'5'	2000	150	2150
'6'	2000	150	2150
'7'	2000	150	2150
'8'	2000	150	2150
'9'	2000	150	2150
All	20000	1500	21500

Methods Description

A. Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA)

In QDA the boundary between classes can be quadratic:

$$b1x1^2 + b12x1x2 + \dots + a1x1 + a2x2 + \dots + anxn + b = 0$$

Interestingly, the QDA predictions are accurate almost 60% of the time, even though the 2005 data was not used to fit the model. This level of accuracy is quite impressive for stock market data, which is known to be quite hard to model accurately

B. Random Forest Classifier (RFC), It consists in a general MCS building method using Decision Trees as base classifiers. The particularity of this ensemble is that each of them has to be built from a set of random parameters. The main idea is that this randomization introduces more diversity into the base classifiers ensemble. The definition given by Breiman in this paper is deliberately generic enough to let this randomization be introduced anywhere in the process. Therefore a RF could be built by sampling the feature set (like in Random Subspace principle), the data set (like in Bagging principle),

and/or just varying randomly some parameters of the trees.

- C. Decision Tree Classifier (DTC), Decision Tree using Spark's distributed implementation. It gives the reader a better understanding of some critical hyperparameters for the tree learning algorithm, using examples to demonstrate how tuning the hyperparameters can improve accuracy. Decision tree learning uses a decision tree (as a predictive model) to go from observations about an item (represented in the branches) to conclusions about the item's target value (represented in the leaves).

- D. A multilayer perceptron (MLP) is a class of feedforward artificial neural network. An MLP consists of, at least, three layers of nodes: an input layer, a hidden layer and an output layer. Except for the input nodes, each node is a neuron that uses a nonlinear activation function. MLP utilizes a supervised learning technique called backpropagation for training.^{[1][2]} Its multiple layers and non-linear activation distinguish MLP from a linear perceptron. It can distinguish data that is not linearly separable.

Multi-layer Perceptron w. 1 hidden layer (logistic sigmoid)

III. EVALUATION RESULT

TABLE I
EVALUATION METHODS

METHODS	ACCURACY	PRE	RECALL	F1
QDA	67.20	58	67	61
RFC	90.40	91	90	90
DTC	78.40	78	78	78
MLP	95.20	95	95	95
SVM	93.13	93	93	93

Impact of training number of data on the accuracy rate, precision, recall, f1-score- 100% of training data means 20000 samples, and 1500 test data

As we see MLP classifier have a more accuracy and better result, also we used confusion matrix to better compare detail of classifiers, A confusion matrix is a table that is often used to describe the performance of a classification model (or "classifier") on a set of test data for which the true values are known. The confusion matrix itself is relatively simple to understand, but the related terminology can be confusing.

A. QDA

D. MLP

B. RFC

E. SVM

C. DTC

IV. CONCLUSION

Research on Handwritten digit recognition back to several decades. Today, cleanly machine-printed text documents with simple layouts can be recognized reliably by off-the-shelf OCR software. As we have seen throughout this paper, there is also some success with handwriting recognition, particularly for isolated hand printed characters and words. For example, in the on-line case, the recently introduced PDAs have practical value. Similarly, some on-line signature verification systems have been marketed over the last few years and instructional tools to help children learn to write are beginning to emerge. In this work, QDA, RFC, DTC, MLP and SVM is proposed for the classification of the standard base USPS isolated digit. An extraction technique is used in the phase of extraction of characteristics before implementing the classification of the digits. The recognition rate is avg is more

than 80.00% with a Test database containing 1,500 samples and. the method of extraction shows enough good results.

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